

Nov to May compared with Jul-Sep. Irrigation water, air, and soil surfaces are cold. (This also affects labor productivity.)

We screened 100 rice lines for cold tolerance in 1987-88. Lines were seeded 18 Dec 1987. Eight failed to germinate. Seedlings in the nursery exhibited stunted growth, leaf yellowing, scorched leaf tips, retarded tillering, and poor root development.

Seedlings were transplanted 18 Feb 1988 in nonreplicated 4 × 6-m microplots. Average plant height at transplanting was 6 cm. Twenty entries died after transplanting.

Irrigation was from tubewells, and was maintained at 13-15 cm depth. As general weather conditions improved toward the end of Feb, seedlings became more vigorous.

Eight entries had 100% empty glumes; incidence of sterility in the remaining 64 entries ranged from 18 to 60%. This may be attributed to high temperature and high winds at anthesis in late Mar to early Apr.

Plant height at maturity ranged from 69.4 to 95.0 cm; days to 50% flowering ranged from 105 to 142 (Table 2).

The best 18 entries were selected for further advanced yield trials 1988-89. ■

Table 2. Growth characteristics and grain yield of cultivars selected for cold tolerance.^a Nigeria, 1987-88.

Cultivar ^a	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield g/pot (2.4m ²)
RNR74229	122	83.3	1380
RTN76-2-1-1-1	127	90.4	1300
IR13538-48-2-3-2	115	79.2	1230
IR27325063-2-2	122	84.4	1180
BR161-23-59	122	75.2	1180
FAROX233-1-1-3	127	82.2	1160
C1321-2	122	72.4	1140
IR24594-272-2-2	121	95.0	1120
KUA1727	127	90.6	1120
BG367-4	105	84.4	1100
IR28210-68-4-1-3	109	80.2	1100
IR28118-138-2-3	142	90.4	1100
ITA302	122	83.4	1080
ITA121	111	69.4	1060
C1158-7	138	77.4	1040
16439	116	74.4	1040
BG276-5	105	80.0	1000
ET6279	122	80.2	1000

^aCold tolerance score for these entries is 5 by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Phosphorus activity in genotypes with low phosphorus tolerance

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Seven P-tolerant varieties (IR28, IR29, IR30, Khonorullo, Mirikrak, Pawnbuh, and Ngoba) and their 21 cross combinations made in a diallel fashion without reciprocals were sown in upland lateritic soil deficient in P (5 ppm available P, pH 5.0). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Spacing was 20 cm between plants and between rows.

Plant tissue analysis was done 60 d after seeding (leaf) and at harvest (root, leaf, stem, panicle without grain, and sound grain). Genotypic and phenotypic

correlation coefficients were estimated, and path analysis done.

P content in leaf at 60 d showed a significant negative correlation ($r_g = -0.413$) with sound grain P (see table); other correlations were not significant. Root P had a significant, positive association with P content in stem ($r_p = 0.603$, $r_g = 0.722$), leaf ($r_p = 0.419$, $r_g = 0.507$), and sound grain ($r_p = 0.525$, $r_g = 0.588$) at both the phenotypic and genotypic levels. A significant, positive association was found between P content in stem and leaf at harvest; that between grain yield and plant was significant and negative at phenotypic and genotypic levels.

The effect of P activity through different pathways and its role in yield was determined using genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients. The genotypic correlation had a higher magnitude. The highest direct positive contribution was made by P in the root

Phenotypic and genotypic correlation^a coefficients of P content in leaf at 60 d growth, different organs at harvest, and grain yield per plant and direct contributions to yield.

	Correlation coefficients of P content ^b						Direct effect
	At 60 d growth			At harvest			
	Leaf	Root	Stem	Leaf	Panicle without grain	Grain	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	
(1)							0.230 0.280
(2) r_p	-0.093						0.211
r_g	-0.112						0.337
(3) r_p	0.044	0.603**					0.051
r_g	0.070	0.722**					0.080
(4) r_p	0.184	0.419*	0.634**				-0.514
r_g	0.185	0.507**	0.726**				-0.669
(5) r_p	-0.292	0.057	0.062	0.260			0.028
r_g	-0.347	0.075	0.065	0.288			0.038
(6) r_p	-0.353	0.525**	0.332	0.292	0.237		-0.080
r_g	-0.413*	0.588**	0.359	0.303	0.241		-0.135
(7) r_p^c	0.154	-0.039	-0.166	-0.382*	-0.232	-0.190	-
r_g^c	0.167	-0.052	-0.189	-0.418*	-0.255	-0.217	-

^a r_p , r_g phenotypic and genotypic correlation coefficients. ^bSignificant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ^cFor grain yield/plant.

(0.337) at harvest, followed by P in leaf at 60 d and in stem at harvest. The indirect effects of P in stem, grain, leaf, and sterile panicles via root were all

positive. An indirect positive effect was found via stem at harvest. The direct and indirect contributions of leaf and sound grain were negative. ■

Manoharsali as checks were field tested at research stations and in field trials in Gerua, Tinsukia, and Suklivoria for 1-6 yr. Trials were laid out at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings/hill. Forty kg N as urea was applied in three splits before planting, at tillering, and at panicle initiation; 20 kg/ha each of P and K were applied in the form of single superphosphate and muriate of potash as basal.

IET6666 showed wide adaptability and stability in grain yield under the agroecological conditions of Assam (Table 2). It flowered in 115-120 d and matured in 145-157 d.

The variety is being evaluated for release as Lakhimi for Assam wet season. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement

IET6666, a new high-yielding rice variety for Assam

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IET6666, a long-duration, high-yielding variety evolved from RP31-49-2/Patnai

23 by the Directorate of Rice Research in Hyderabad, is suitable for low-lying fields and cloudy weather conditions during wet season. Its coarse grain and intermediate plant height are preferred by the majority of farmers in Assam.

Agronomic characteristics are given in Table 1.

IET6666, 12 other promising cultivars with similar duration, and Mahsuri and

Table 1. Morphological and physiological characteristics of IET6666 and check variety Manoharsali at Titabar, Assam, India.

Character	IET6666	Manoharsali
Plant height (cm)	118.73	148.53
Duration	145	148
Panicles (no./m ²)	257	242
Filled grains (no./panicle)	103	83
1000-grain weight (g)	23.22	24.55
Total dry matter at flowering (kg/ha)	116.76	146.56
Leaf area index	4.58	5.80
Total chlorophyll content at flowering (mg/g fresh wt)	2.23	3.43
N content in leaf tissues at flowering (%)	2.18	1.23
Solar energy utilization efficiency for dry matter (%)	1.87	0.81
Solar energy utilization for grain yield (%)	0.55	0.25

Table 2. Yields of IET6666 and check varieties at different locations in Assam, India 1978-88.

Year	Location	Yield (t/ha)		
		IET6666	Mahsuri	Manoharsali
1978	Titabar	3.4	2.7	-
	Karimganj	3.0	3.3	-
1979	Titabar	5.2	3.8	-
	Karimganj	2.9	3.9	-
1980	Titabar	5.0	4.5	-
	Karimganj	3.6	3.5	-
1982	Titabar	3.8	-	3.0
	Karimganj	4.4	-	1.9
1983	Titabar	3.9	-	2.0
	Karimganj	4.4	-	3.5
1984	Titabar	5.3	-	3.1
1985	Titabar	5.3	-	3.2
1986	Titabar	5.2	-	3.2
1987	Titabar	5.4	-	3.2
1988	Titabar	5.1	-	2.6
1984 on-farm trials	Gerua	6.4	-	5.2
	Tinsukia	5.1	-	4.2
	Suklivoria	3.9	-	4.0

Performance of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 under transplanted rainfed lowland conditions in Nepal

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In Nepal, 88% of the rice area (1.45 million ha in 1988) is in the subtropical climatic region of the Tarai belt (67-250 m altitude), the Inner Tarai region, and equivalent climatic region of river basin areas and valleys up to 900 m altitude.

Table 1. Yields of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 at 4 sites in subtropical Nepal, 1983-86.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Increase over check(%)	Experiment site ^a and time
	Tarahara	Parwanipur	Rampur	Nepalganj	Mean		
IR46	4.6	2.6	3.0	3.2	3.4	142	Research stations, 1983-84
Improved check Bindeshori	2.4	2.2	2.0	2.8	2.4	100	
IR46	4.8	2.6	2.4	4.2 ^a	3.5	114	Farmers' fields, 1985-86
Improved check Masuli	3.3	2.0	-	3.9	3.1	100	
IR10781	3918	2956	2692	2981	3.1	105	Research stations, 1984-85
Improved check Bindeshori	3562	3001	2512	2897	3.0	100	
IR10781	4840	2818	3750	4150	3.9	127	Farmers' fields, 1985-86
Improved check Masuli	3292	2012	-	3900	3.1	100	

^a Farmer's field result of this location is from Nawal Parasi area. Each location includes the results from various farmers' fields.